

TO`RTBURCHAK ELEMENT USTIDA GAUSS – LEJANDR FORMULASI

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Gauss kvadraturalari matematika, fizika, injineriya va boshqa sohalarda juda muhim bo`lgan bir tushunchadir. Hisoblash matematikasi sohasida nazariy izlanishlar asosan, tipik matematik masalalarni yechishning sonli metodlar atrofida guruhlanadi. Bu sohaning klassik masalalaridan biri bu integrallarni taqribiy hisoblash formulalarini qurishdan iborat. Bir karrali integrallarni son qiymatlari geometrik nuqtai nazardan qisqacha kvadratura deb ataladi.

Bunday masalalar bilan ko`pincha buyuk olimlar shug`ullanganlar. Masalan: Gauss, Chebishev, Eylar, Nyuton va boshqalar.

Kvadratur formular deganda quyidagi taqribiy tenglikni tushunamiz:

$$\int_B f(x)dx \approx \sum_{\lambda=1}^N C_{\lambda} f(x^{(\lambda)}), \quad (1)$$

bu yerda C_{λ} – kvadratur formulaning koeffisientlari, $x^{(\lambda)}$ – tugun nuqtalari, N – tugun nuqtalar soni. Integralning eng sodda taqribiy ifodasi asosan $[a, b]$ kesma balandligi $f(x)$ ning $\frac{a+b}{2}$ nuqtadagi $f(\frac{a+b}{2})$ qiymatiga teng bo`lgan to`g`ri turtburchak yuzasining kattaligidan iborat.

Quyidagi kvadratur formulani hosil qilamiz.

$$\int_a^b f(x)dx \approx (b-a)f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right), \quad (2)$$

Katta nazariy va amaliy ahamiyatga ega bo`lgan kvadratur formulalar bilan bog`liq hisoblash algoritmlarini optimizizastiyalash masalalari bilan ko`pgina olimlar shug`ullanib kelgan. Bulardan S.L.Sobolev, A.N.Kolmogorov, S.M.Nikolskiy va boshqalar.

ALGEBRAIK ANIQLIGI YUQORI BO`LGAN KVADRATUR FORMULALAR.

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1(a) – rasmda ko`rsatilgan to`rtburchaklar element ustidagi qo`sh integral

$$I = \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 f(\xi, \eta) d\eta d\xi \quad (1)$$

ni ko`rib chiqamiz. Har bir integralni Gauss –Legendre kvadraturasi bo`yicha har bir koordinata yo`nalishida $n + 1$ integral nuqtalari yordamida baholab, biz

$$I = \int_{-1}^1 \sum_{i=0}^n f(\xi, \eta) d\eta = \sum_{j=0}^n A_j \left[\sum_{i=0}^n A_i f(\xi_i, \eta_i) \right] \quad (2)$$

yoki

$$I = \sum_{i=0}^n \sum_{j=0}^n A_i A_j f(\xi, \eta) \quad (3)$$

ni olamiz.

Yuqorida ta'kidlab o'tilganidek, har bir koordinata yo'nalishidagi $m = n + 1$ integrallash nuqtalari soni integrallash tartibi deb ataladi. (1.a) - rasmda uchinchi tartibli integrallash qo'llaniladigan integrallash nuqtalarining joylashuvi ko'rsatilgan ($m = 3$).

(1.b) - rasmdagi to'rtburchak elementga kvadraturani qo'llash uchun avvalo to'rtburchakni (1.a) - rasmdagi "standart" to'rtburchakka solishimiz kerak. Xaritaga solish deganda biz to'rtburchak va to'rtburchakdagi nuqtalar o'rtasida birma - bir mos keladigan $x = x(\xi, \eta), y = y(\xi, \eta)$ koordinata o'zgarishini tushunamiz.

1 rasm. To'rtburchakni to'rtburchakga aylantirish.

Vazifani bajaradigan transformatsiya

$$x(\xi, \eta) = \sum_{k=1}^4 N_k(\xi, \eta) x_k \quad y(\xi, \eta) = \sum_{k=1}^4 N_k(\xi, \eta) y_k \quad (4)$$

bu yerda (x_k, y_k) to'rtburchakning k burchagi va

$$\begin{aligned}N_1(\xi, \eta) &= \frac{1}{4}(1 - \xi)(1 - \eta) \\N_2(\xi, \eta) &= \frac{1}{4}(1 + \xi)(1 - \eta) \\N_3(\xi, \eta) &= \frac{1}{4}(1 + \xi)(1 + \eta) \\N_4(\xi, \eta) &= \frac{1}{4}(1 - \xi)(1 + \eta)\end{aligned}\tag{5}$$

koordinatalari.

Shakl funksiyalari deb nomlanuvchi $N_k(\xi, \eta)$ funktsiyalari ikki chiziqli (har bir koordinatada chiziqli). Shunday qilib, to`g`ri chiziqlar xaritada to`g`ri bo`lib qoladi. Xususan, to`rtburchakning tomonlari $\xi = \pm 1$ va $\eta = \pm 1$ chiziq'larga tushirilgan.

Xaritalash maydonlarni buzganligi sababli, to`rtburchakning cheksiz kichik maydoni elementi  $dA = dx dy$  to`rtburchakning tengdoshi $dA' = d\xi d\eta$ bilan teng emas. Sohalar orasidagi munosabat

$$dx dy = |J(\xi, \eta)| d\xi d\eta\tag{6}$$

ekanligini ko`rsatish mumkin.

Bu yerda

$$J(\xi, \eta) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi} & \frac{\partial y}{\partial \xi} \\ \frac{\partial x}{\partial \eta} & \frac{\partial y}{\partial \eta} \end{bmatrix}\tag{7 a}$$

xaritalashning Yakobiy matritsasi sifatida tanilgan. (4) va (5) tenglamalarni almashtirib, differensiallashda Yakobiy matritsasining komponentlari:

$$\begin{aligned}J_{11} &= \frac{1}{4}[-(1 - \eta)x_1 + (1 - \eta)x_2 + (1 + \eta)x_3 - (1 - \eta)x_4] \\J_{12} &= \frac{1}{4}[-(1 - \eta)y_1 + (1 - \eta)y_2 + (1 + \eta)y_3 - (1 - \eta)y_4] \\J_{21} &= \frac{1}{4}[-(1 - \xi)x_1 - (1 + \xi)x_2 + (1 + \xi)x_3 + (1 - \xi)x_4] \\J_{22} &= \frac{1}{4}[-(1 - \xi)y_1 - (1 + \xi)y_2 + (1 + \xi)y_3 + (1 - \xi)y_4]\end{aligned}\tag{7 b}$$

bo`ladi. Endi biz

$$\iint_A f(x,y)dx dy = \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 f[x(\xi,\eta),y(\xi,\eta)]J(\xi,\eta)d\xi d\eta \quad (8)$$

yo'zishimiz mumkin.

O'ng tomonli integral "standart" to'rtburchaklar ustidan olinganligi sababli, uni (3) tenglama yordamida hisoblash mumkin. (3) tenglamadagi $f(\xi,\eta)$ ni (8) tenglamadagi integralga almashtirsak, to'rtburchak soha bo'yicha Gauss Legendre kvadraturasining quyidagi formulasini olamiz:

$$I = \sum_{i=0}^n \sum_{j=0}^n A_i A_j f[x(\xi_i, \eta_j), y(\xi_i, \eta_j)] J(\xi_i, \eta_j) \quad (9)$$

Integrallash nuqtalarining ξ va η -koordinatalari va vaznlarni yana 2.3 - jadvaldan olish mumkin.

- gaussQuad2

Ushbu modulda `gaussQuad2` funksiyasi m integratsiya tartibli Gauss - Legendre kvadraturasi bo'lgan to'rtburchak element bo'yicha $\iint_A f(x,y)dx dy$ ni hisoblaydi. To'rtburchak x va y massivlari bilan belgilanadi, ular element atrofida soat miliga teskari yo'nalishda tartiblangan to'rtta burchakning koordinatalarini o'z ichiga oladi. Yakobiy matritsaning determinanti jac funksiyasini chaqirish orqali olinadi; xaritalash xarita orqali amalga oshiriladi. Integratsiya nuqtalaridagi vaznlar va ξ va η qiymatlari oldingi bo'limda sanab o'tilgan Gauss tugunlari tomonidan hisoblanadi (ξ va η ro'yxatda S va t sifatida ko'rinadi).

```
## module gaussQuad2
```

```
`` I = gaussQuad2(f,xc,yc,m).
```

Gauss -Legendre integrallash tartibi m yordamida

$f(x, y)$ ning to'rtburchak ustidagi integratsiyasi.

$\{xc\}, \{yc\}$ to'rtburchakning burchak koordinatalari.

```
``
```

```
from gaussNodes import *
```

```
import numpy as np
```

```
def gaussQuad2(f,x,y,m):
```

```
def jac(x,y,s,t):
```

```
J = np.zeros((2,2))
```



```

J[0,0] = -(1.0 - t)*x[0] + (1.0 - t)*x[1] \
+ (1.0 + t)*x[2] - (1.0 + t)*x[3]
J[0,1] = -(1.0 - t)*y[0] + (1.0 - t)*y[1] \
+ (1.0 + t)*y[2] - (1.0 + t)*y[3]
J[1,0] = -(1.0 - s)*x[0] - (1.0 + s)*x[1] \
+ (1.0 + s)*x[2] + (1.0 - s)*x[3]
J[1,1] = -(1.0 - s)*y[0] - (1.0 + s)*y[1] \
+ (1.0 + s)*y[2] + (1.0 - s)*y[3]
return (J[0,0]*J[1,1] - J[0,1]*J[1,0])/16.0
def map(x,y,s,t):
N = np.zeros(4)
N[0] = (1.0 - s)*(1.0 - t)/4.0
N[1] = (1.0 + s)*(1.0 - t)/4.0
N[2] = (1.0 + s)*(1.0 + t)/4.0
N[3] = (1.0 - s)*(1.0 + t)/4.0
xCoord = np.dot(N,x)
yCoord = np.dot(N,y)
return xCoord,yCoord
s,A = gaussNodes(m)
sum = 0.0
for i in range(m):
for j in range(m):
xCoord,yCoord = map(x,y,s[i],s[j])
sum = sum + A[i]*A[j]*jac(x,y,s[i],s[j]) \
*f(xCoord,yCoord)
return sum

```

3.1. Misol

2. – rasm.

$I = \iint_A (x^2 + y^2) dx dy$ integralini avval ko`rsatilgan to`rtburchak A sohadan

“standart” to`rtburchakka aylantirib, analitik tarzda baholaymiz.

Masalaning yechimi. To`rtburchakning burchak koordinatalari

$$x^T = [0 \quad 2 \quad 2 \quad 0] \quad y^T = [0 \quad 0 \quad 3 \quad 2]$$

Xaritalash

$$x(\xi, \eta) = \sum_{k=1}^4 N_k(\xi, \eta) x_k = 0 + \frac{(1+\xi)(1-\eta)}{4}(2) + \frac{(1+\xi)(1+\eta)}{4}(2) + 0 = 1 + \xi$$

$$y(\xi, \eta) = \sum_{k=1}^4 N_k(\xi, \eta) y_k = 0 + 0 + \frac{(1+\xi)(1+\eta)}{4}(3) + \frac{(1-\xi)(1+\eta)}{4}(2) = \frac{(5+\xi)(1+\eta)}{4}$$

bo`lib, Yakobiy matritsasi

$$J(\xi, \eta) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi} & \frac{\partial y}{\partial \xi} \\ \frac{\partial x}{\partial \eta} & \frac{\partial y}{\partial \eta} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \frac{1+\eta}{4} \\ 0 & \frac{5+\xi}{4} \end{bmatrix}$$

uchun hosil bo`ladi. Shunday qilib, maydon masshtab koeffitsienti

$$|J(\xi, \eta)| = \frac{5+\xi}{4}$$

Endi biz integralni to`rtburchakdan standart to`rtburchakgacha xaritalashimiz mumkin. Tenglama (8) ga murojaat qilib, biz

$$I = \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 \left[\left(\frac{1+\xi}{2} \right)^2 + \frac{(5+\xi)(1+\eta)}{4} \right] \frac{5+\xi}{4} d\xi d\eta =$$

$$= \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 \left(\frac{15}{8} + \frac{21}{16} \xi + \frac{1}{2} \xi^2 + \frac{1}{16} \xi^3 + \frac{25}{16} \eta + \frac{5}{8} \xi \eta + \frac{1}{16} \xi^2 \eta \right) d\xi d\eta$$

ni olamiz, faqat ξ va η ning teng darajalari integralga hissa qo`shishini hisobga olsak, integral

$$I = \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 \left(\frac{15}{8} + \frac{1}{2} \xi^2 \right) d\xi d\eta = \frac{49}{6}$$

ni soddalashtiradi.

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